

The Impact of the Syrian Crisis on the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) Region

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ABSTRACT

In the paper, the Syrian conflict caused a direct effect on the Middle East and North African (MENA) Region. The attention on an escalation of tensions between Bashar al-Assad's government and opposition as a source of civil war in Syria was paid. The internal and external factors were shown as main contractors in the conflicts. Also, The war has led to catastrophic consequences to the neighbouring countries like refugees crisis.

The paper assessed the factors underlying the spillover and the consequence of the crisis especially the political and security consequences and its prospect on the region, This paper addressed the situation in Syria as a fragile state. Also will explore the factors that contributed to the spillover effect the Syrian Crisis, discuss the consequences of the conflict in the MENA region. Also, the paper will emphasize the reasons why the Syrian revolution failed and why Egyptian revolutions passed, in a comparison Syria with Egypt as a benchmark, and set implications to end the civil war in Syria.

The paper recommends starting national reconciliation and dialogue among different political organizations under UN and Arab league mediation. Also, the paper recommends the future of conflict consequences.

Keywords: SYRIA, SPILLOVER, CONFLICT, FRAGILE, MENA, EGYPT, REVOLUTION, CONSEQUENCES

Introduction

The wave of revolutions in the Middle East & North Africa (MENA) region erupted by the end of 2010, and the beginning of 2011 known as the Arab Spring with a purpose of overthrowing the most powerful, long-lasting, and reactive violent regimes in Tunisia, Egypt, Syria, Libya, and Yemen. In March 2011 (Ivanciu, 2016). The protests broke out in Syria were inspired by similar protests throughout the MENA. Al Assad's regime in Syria responded strongly to the peaceful protests and exacerbated the situation. His regime unleashed security and intelligence services to disperse rallies and demonstrations, often with live fire, and to capture dissidents. After that, the events took a terrible turn (Mariwala, 2014). By the end of 2011, the armed conflict between government forces and opposition rebels began. In the war, the Syrian regime - especially

the ruling elite Alawites and the state apparatus - stands in the face of a coalition of opposition insurgents - mostly Sunnis. However, the complexity of the war has intensified due to the interference of global and regional powers as well as Islamic Jihadists in the confusion.

The armed conflict causes repression against citizens acted by the regime of President Bashar Al-Assad, who ruled from 2000, without proposing political and social changes in Syria.

The violence was escalating and the civil war broke out. The armed conflict showed the reality of social divisions in Syrian. The majority of Syrians are Sunni Muslims, but they were condemned under a repressive security system founded by the Alawites sect to which Bashar Al-Assad belongs to them. Sectarianism was a feature that occurred during the civil conflict in Syria. Where you find some regional governments in the region supported Al-Assad like Iran, the Shiite sect in Iraq, and the Lebanese Hezbollah, while Sunni-majority countries, including Saudi Arabia, Turkey, and Qatar supported the rebels against Al-Assad (Vekalet et al., 2017). Foreign intervention has played a major role in Syria's civil conflict, but ironically, it has escalated the conflict and prolonged the ongoing civil war.

Some countries supported Syria in the war against the Islamic State of Iraq and Syria (ISIS), but encouragement for Al-Assad's regime was not clear. Syria now considers as a highly fragile state in the OECD state fragility index in 2018 more than 8 years of civil war destroyed the Syrian economy and caused more than five million refugees around the region. In addition to security issues that threaten not only Syria but the entire MENA region. Political conflict and external intervention were one of the main triggers that make the conflict more complex and complicated.

This paper will address the situation in Syria as a fragile state. Also will explore the factors that contributed to the spillover effect the Syrian Crisis, discuss the consequences of the conflict. Also, the paper will emphasize the reasons why the Syrian revolution failed and why Egyptian revolutions passed, in a comparison Syria with Egypt as a benchmark, and set implications to end the civil war in Syria.

Materials and methods

PROBLEM STATEMENT

The Syrian conflict has caused one of the world's most pressing humanitarian situations in decades with more than five million Syrian fleeings to neighbouring countries. Unless a viable solution is developed, it will be a regional threat to peace and security in the future. This paper assesses the factors underlying the spillover and the consequence of the crisis especially the political and security consequences and its prospect on the region.

1. FACTORS THAT CONTRIBUTED TO THE SPILLOVER EFFECT IN THE SYRIAN CRISIS

1.1.EXTERNAL FACTORS

1.1.1. INFLUENCE OF ARAB SPRING

The Arab Spring was one of the main triggers to ignite the conflict in Syria, it started in Tunisia where the citizens collapsed of a totalitarian regime and the outburst of streets demanding for freedom and their right, as well as the actions chosen by the various parties, led to the rapid escalation of initial protests from civil unrest to intense armed conflict. The Arab Spring protests generate the hope and spirit in the Syrian citizens to have a new era in Syria like the other Arab Spring countries. Minor protests began immediately in March 2011 after the initial protests in Cairo in January 2011, and the following months the number of the protests increased within the country by the summer of 2011, where the armed conflict has already begun between the protests and Al-Assad's regime (Zuber & Moussa, 2018).

1.1.2. FRAGILITY OF NEIGHBORING STATES

The comparative stability of governing institutions in countries bordering conflict areas is a second major factor leading to the spread of violence. The spread of conflict could lead to further repression in Syria, causing some form of pre-emptive repression. Unstable regimes in Iraq lie alongside the states of conflict. The Islamic jihadists in Iraq joined the Syrian civil war. Although a large number of jihadi groups are involved in the war, the Islamic state was the main risk holder in the conflict (Asseburg, 2013).

1.1.3. EXTERNAL SUPPORT/MILITARY

External support or international intervention is a major contributor to the spread of conflict. The act of external support (either to the national or opposition state) does not only increase the likelihood of the spread of the conflict but may also increase the duration of the conflict (Vekalet et al., 2017). Once a third party enters the dispute on either side, the other party considers it an additional enemy seeking to disrupt the battle balance. For example, in Syria, world powers add fuel to the fire. Every foreign power has waged a proxy war in Syria for its narrow interests (Uludag, 2015). Furthermore, Saudi Arabia and Qatar are funding the rebels for clearly sectarian reasons. They are striving for the formation of a Sunni government in Syria.

Iran, on the other hand, seeks to protect Assad by providing financial and military support. Iran's drives are to maintain the Shia regime in Syria, strengthen its role in the Arab world in supplying weapons and send some of its senior military personnel, including General Qassem Soleimani, to the Syrian battlefields (Filkins 2013). The West supports opposition forces that are believed to be "adequate" and do not include Al-Nusra. These countries, including the US, UK, and France, support the opposition to overthrow the regime. The West publicly called on Assad to step down and called for the democratization of Syria (Vekalet et al., 2017). Al-Assad's regime was supported by the Lebanese Hezbollah led by Hassan Nasrallah. Hezbollah offers fighters to Al-Assad, because of common sectoral identity (the fact that the Alawites are a subset of Shias) and because of Assad's support for Hezbollah in the past, especially during the Israeli-Lebanese conflict in 2006 (Uludag, 2015).

1.1.4. REFUGEE/POPULATION MOVEMENTS

The displacement of civilians from the troubled country consider as a contributing factor to the conflict. Such movements directly and negatively affect the receiving state. Researchers assumed that refugee movements may not only be the result of ongoing civil war but may also be the cause of many conflicts (Carpenter, 2013). While the exact mechanism by which refugees turn into civil wars or rebellions is still under investigation, their relationship is clear. The refugee crisis is not merely a Syrian problem; on the contrary, all neighbouring countries are deeply affected, the European Union is strained by the constant influx of asylum-seekers and the burden is not equally shared by all international actors involved in the conflict. Since 2011, 4,863,684 Syrians have been registered by the UNHCR on 19 January 2017, while 6.3 million are internally displaced. Refugees, asylum-seekers, and migrants are now spread all over the world in the hope of finding better conditions. Not all countries have responded in the same way, and more and more nations are beginning to turn their back to the fleeing masses (Ferris & Kirişci, 2016).

1.2. INTERNAL FACTORS

1.2.1. ETHNIC AND MINORITY RELATIONSHIPS

Common ethnicity is a major variable when assessing the probability of indirect propagation across a given region. Linking ethnic relations literature, not only with the spread of conflict through external and cultural support but also in increasing collective awareness among opposition groups. For example, violence against some groups in neighbouring countries may raise awareness at home or raise strong expectations from their government regarding fair treatment or representation (Mariwala, 2014).

Ethnic divisions were appreciated and proved important in explaining the beginning of the conflict and the creation of rebellion. The Syrian regime is acting to deter some ethnic groups from standing up to opposition forces. The first major player in the Syrian civil war is the ruling coalition led by Bashar Al-Assad.

The Alawites, who make up 10% to 15% of the Syrian people, have supported Assad since the beginning of the civil war. The Druze are another minority tribe in Syria believed to have provided substantial support in the form of Assad's power until recently when Druze leaders announced they would stop supporting the Assad regime and protect themselves from any insurgent attack (Aziz, Mada, Anindita, & Mada, 2017). The Kurds are an ethnic group that has been divided into three states during the colonial frontier. They live primarily along the border between Iraq, Iran, Syria, and Turkey. They have been fighting for a long time to establish independent Kurdistan in these countries, but they have not succeeded to a large extent. However, with the instability and vacuum caused by the unrest in Syria, the dream of independent Kurdistan has rebounded. Therefore, the first objective of the Syrian Kurds is to occupy the Kurdish areas during the civil war and negotiate for the establishment of an autonomous Kurdish region inside Syria after the war. They have largely come out of the conflict between the government and the opposition, but Assad has shown no tolerance for them. Assad has strongly opposed the formation of an independent Kurdish region (Mariwala, 2014).

1.2.2. GOVERNMENT AND DISSATISFIED CAPABILITIES

The efficiency of the Syrian army has a direct impact on the possibility of indirect proliferation. The ability of the Syrian government and its readiness to carry out operations may lead to a rapid defeat of the opposition or lead to a long-term conflict. In addition to. The ability of rebels or opposition groups to provide, deploy and implement operations is crucial in assessing the likelihood of consequences (Uludag, 2015). Research has shown that third-party or internal intervention becomes more likely when opposition groups or insurgent groups are ethnically different from the aggressor. Intervention on the opposition side may increase the legitimacy of the group, which can then attract more members and prolong the conflict. The indirect effects of refugee camps provide fertile grounds for recruitment once the legitimacy of their case has been established.

2. THE CONSEQUENCES OF THE CONFLICT

2.1. THE SYRIAN REFUGEE AND MIGRATION CRISIS

The war created a massive refugee crisis. Millions of Syrians have been displaced from their homes because of the war. According to the UN, about 13.5 million people need humanitarian assistance in Syria. It also announced that the number of IDPs in Syria is about 6.3 million, while the number of people who fled the country is about 4.8 million (Azad, 2016).

2.2. THE ABRUPT NEIGHBOURHOOD

The Syrian refugee crisis is a major challenge for recipient countries, especially in the immediate vicinity. The region (i.e. Turkey, Jordan, Iraq, Egypt, and Lebanon) as a whole comprises more than 4.5 million refugees (UNHCR, 2017).

Table (1) Total Registered Syrian Refugee Population, by Country-Region, 2012–16

<i>Country</i>	<i>Jan 2012</i>	<i>Dec 2013</i>	<i>Dec 2014</i>	<i>Dec 2015</i>	<i>Dec 2016</i>
<i>Lebanon</i>	<i>6.916</i>	<i>138.213</i>	<i>884.017</i>	<i>1.159.396</i>	<i>1.011.366</i>
<i>Jordan</i>	<i>4.013</i>	<i>116.778</i>	<i>576.354</i>	<i>623.338</i>	<i>655.496</i>
<i>Iraq</i>	<i>180</i>	<i>66.920</i>	<i>213.223</i>	<i>233.625</i>	<i>230.836</i>
<i>Egypt, Arab Rep.</i>	<i>924</i>	<i>12.836</i>	<i>131.707</i>	<i>138.212</i>	<i>116.013</i>
<i>Turkey</i>	<i>9.500</i>	<i>174.598</i>	<i>560.129</i>	<i>1.622.839</i>	<i>2.814.631</i>
<i>North Africa</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>N/A</i>	<i>29.275</i>
<i>Total</i>	<i>21.533</i>	<i>509.345</i>	<i>2.365.430</i>	<i>3.777.410</i>	<i>4.857.617</i>

Source: UNHCR, 2017

Turkey: Among the five countries hosting Syrian refugees, Turkish institutions are the most responsive. The services provided inside and outside the camp are coordinated by the General Directorate of Immigration Department (DGMM) of the Turkish Ministry of the Interior. DGMM notes that in the last six years the government has spent \$ 12 billion on Syrian refugees - who make up about 4% of the country's population. The domestic legal rights of Syrian and Iraqi refugees continue to expand throughout Turkey, and Turkish President Erdogan has indicated that Turkish refugees can be granted Turkish citizenship in the future.

Jordan: There may not be a bigger symbol of the size of the Syrian refugee crisis than the Zaatari refugee camp in Jordan, which was once the fourth largest city in the country. Zaatari's population peaked in 2013, and now numbers about 70,000 (UNHCR, 2016). Refugees represent 10% of the country's population. Jordan, like Lebanon, is familiar with refugees based on its experience with the Palestinians. United Nations agencies, the Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation of the Government of Jordan and NGO partners are implementing a unique national plan in Jordan. The Jordan Response Plan (JRP) aims to coordinate humanitarian assistance activities throughout the country. The unique aspect of the JRP program is the creation of several Special Economic Zones to support the livelihoods of Syrian refugees over the medium term (Young, Stebbins, Frederick, & Shahery, 2018).

Iraq: Face unique challenges compared to other the Middle East and North Africa countries, because while hosting Syrian refugees, there are more than 3 million internally displaced and some 220,000 refugees outside the borders of Iraq (UNHCR, 2017). The Kurdistan Ministry of Displacement and Migration and the Ministry of Interior of the Kurdistan Regional Government (KRG) work in close coordination with UNHCR to provide humanitarian assistance to displaced Arabs and Kurds (UNHCR, 2017). Coordination with the KRG is due to the fact that while some Syrians are being transferred to Anbar and Baghdad, most of the Syrian refugees live in the predominantly Kurdish north (UNHCR, 2017).

Egypt: Hosts a limited number of Syrian refugees in Cairo and Giza (UNHCR, 2017). The Egyptian government allows Syrians full access to public education, health care and even services supported by the Egyptian government, including food, energy, and transportation, as they provide Egyptian citizens. The Syrian population in Egypt, through business associations, assists refugees in employment and vocational training (UNHCR, 2017). At the same time, Egypt faces several domestic challenges since the popular uprising in 2011, which challenged good governance and put pressure on Egypt's recovering economy. These challenges may affect Syrian refugees, but they have not been a problem yet because of regional and global support.

Lebanon: The home of most Syrian refugees in the MENA, where the Syrian population is 20% of the country's population of 4.5 million. United Nations agencies, the Ministry of Social Affairs of the Government of Lebanon and NGOs partners coordinated and assisted the protection of Syrian refugees through the Lebanese Crisis Response Plan (LCRP). The United Nations coordinated appeal for

humanitarian assistance to implement LCRP activities amounted to \$ 1.9 billion, half of which funded in 2016 (UNHCR, 2017).

3. SECURITY CONSEQUENCES

The jihadist war in MENA has been particularly strengthened in Syria. These jihadists also kill Christians, blow up the churches and cut off the heads of their enemies. Syria became like Afghanistan in the 1980s. It has become a centre of extremism and extremism where thousands of fighters arrive after leaving their country of origin (Karim, 2017). At present, Sunni and Shia fighters are moving to the battlefield in Syria to participate in the “**holy war**”. These include descendants of Muslim immigrants in Europe who were born and raised there. However, the majority of fighters are from Muslim-majority countries including Pakistan (Warden, 2017).

Since the outbreak of the war in Syria, violence, and terrorism has escalated in Istanbul, Ankara and the southern parts of Turkey. However, Syrian refugees posed a minor threat to Turkey's stability. Turkey has strengthened border security and is building a border wall; however, the state maintains an open border policy with Syria, but most of the official entry points to the country are closed (Duclos, 2017). The authorities open border crossings in humanitarian emergencies. The security crisis resulting from terrorist attacks has weakened popular support for open border policies. Al-Qaeda understood and exploited this trend well: for example, the perpetrators of the attacks at the Stade de France in Paris used false Syrian identity cards. In the absence of an effective regional joint effort to host refugees and reduce economic migration, individual European countries were revisiting their national curricula (Baltes, 2016).

The war has brought devastation to Syria. There has been a huge loss in terms of human deaths and damages to property. According to the Syrian Observatory for Human Rights, since the beginning of the civil war till 13th December 2016, approximately 312,000 persons have been killed. The adjoining table gives a picture of the death toll (Young et al., 2018). In addition to this, around two million people have been injured.

Table (2) Total Death of the conflict until 2016.

TOTAL DEATHS	321.00
CIVILIANS	90.506
SYRIAN ARMY SOLDIERS	60.309
WOMEN	10.540
CHILDREN	15.948
HEZBOLLAH FIGHTERS	1.387
PRO-REGIME MILITIAS	5.330
ISLAMIC JIHADISTS	54.941

Source: UNHCR, 2017

There are already fears that the conflict could destabilize Syria. The collapse of the governmental machinery and the rule of law creates an environment conducive to terrorists, smugglers, and criminals, and creates a safe base for them to pursue transnational activities.

4. WHY SYRIA FAILED WHILE EGYPT PASSED AFTER THE ARAB SPRING

Many factors explain why the Syrian revolution didn't achieve its target like Egypt and Tunisia the paper will present the governance indicators, and security indicators to compare between Egypt and Syria. Egypt's rule-following Mubarak's resignation began with the military, the Security Council of Armed Forces (SCAF). The Egyptian military, due its decades in power, became the most powerful institution in the country. Therefore when the power remained in the hand of the military. They began a series of constitutional amendments that they claim were designed to protect the country "from third party insurgents" that were collaborating to destroy the countries security -notice the similarity in Al-Assad's views as well. Additionally, Syria's sectarian divide played a major role in the escalation of the Syrian conflict, a divide that was not present in Egypt's overwhelming majority Sunni population. Sunni militias began facing off with the government-controlled forces since the initiation of the revolution.

Al-Assad claims that these terrorists or insurgents, where some of them such as Al Nusra Front joined ISIS, have been armed by Western powers and some regional powers. Meanwhile, in Egypt, and due to the conformity of the religious sects of the population, this religion-fueled conflict was not present. Foreign intervention and the flow of arms into Syria had a major effect on the escalation of the conflict. Especially the US, France, Qatar, Saudi Arabia and Turkey implying that these militias were and are armed by these countries and they are looking for Syria's instability. On the other hand, in Egypt, the SCAF maintained the transition from Mubarak to the presidential elections in 2012, where Mohamed Morsi, member of the Muslim Brotherhood party was elected as President. However, after a year in power, his performance was unsatisfactory to the majority of Egyptians and mass protests began on the 30th of June. A coup was staged by, then army removing Mohamed Morsi from the presidential palace.

A period of riots, protests, and terror began by the Muslim Brotherhood and therefore simultaneously a period of mass political arrests began. To maintain control the interim government immediately issued anti-protest laws for unconformity. The cabinet has declared the Muslim Brotherhood group and its organization as a terrorist organization" since the organization has resorted to in Sinai and Metropolitan areas as well. How the Muslim Brotherhood reacted, resorting to violence can be compared with Islamic militia violence in Syria, however on a much smaller scale. Meanwhile how the military, Egyptian people and the interim government reacted to the threat of violence from the extremist Muslim Brotherhood is why the tension was never escalated as it has now in Syria.

4.1.GOVERNANCE INDICATORS IN EGYPT AND SYRIA

Figure (1) Government Effectiveness Egypt and Syria 2018

Source: World Bank Governance indicators in 2018.

Syria is ranked low based on key indicators of government effectiveness compared to Egypt. As shown in **Figure (1)**, Syria hovers at the bottom of the scale or experienced significant deterioration during the 1960s. Similarly, the country is much lower (OECD) and middle-income brackets in the MENA region. These ratings reflect the closed nature of the Syrian regime and the great concentration of power in the executive branch, even according to regional standards (Žuber & Moussa, 2018).

The Syrian performance in management and policy implementation has also been weak concerning other middle-income and middle-income countries in the Middle East and North Africa (MENA) region, although in 2008 the absolute rating showed modest signs of improvement. Studies from this period revealed that the quality of jobs and regulatory services for citizens and businesses were low and steady, and after 2011, the situation has become worse before.

Source: Freedom in the World, Freedom House

Source: Bertelsmann Transformation Index

The revolution of the Mubarak regime by a miscellaneous movement calling for freedom, dignity and social justice has shown a consensus among the main political actors, groups, and parties that aim to end authoritarian policies and social darkness and begin the structural reform of political and economic policies. However, more than 40 political parties have since been established, spanning a wide range of conservative Islamist politicians

to liberal secularists and secular leftists. In many cases, the political aspects of these new actors have yet to be clarified, although key actors agree that democracy is the main form of the political system (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2018).

CONTROL OF CORRUPTION (PERCENTILE RANK)

Source: World Governance Indicators

FREEDOM OF EXPRESSION & BELIEF

Source: Freedom in the World, Freedom House

Similarly, the performance of the state was unfavourable in the indicators of governance and civil liberties during the first decade of the twentieth century. Another important feature of the government landscape in Syria before 2011 is the high levels of corruption in the country and a decline in confidence in public institutions (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2018). Although the country has already surpassed its Middle East and North Africa counterparts, such as Egypt, on both fronts in 2005, the gap widened dramatically by 2010. These trends also undermined citizen trust in public institutions. Gallup surveys from 2009–10 show that the percentage of Syrians expressing trust in key public institutions, such as local police and the judicial system, was lower than comparators. For instance, in 2010, only 48 per cent of Syrians reported trust in local police; in comparison, about 87 per cent of Egyptians responded favourably (Droz-Vincent, 2014).

4.2. SECURITY INDICATORS IN EGYPT AND SYRIA

The strength of the Egyptian Army as an institution, compared to the Syrian military, made the difference when it came to preventing the country from descending into chaos.

Figure (2) Military Expenditure in Egypt & Syria

Source: Our World in Data

Figure (3) Military Personnel

Figure (2) shows that the Egyptian military expenditures are higher than the Syrian Army and exceed 10 billion \$ in the period between the 1970s-1980s during the war with Israel and continue the increase till 2007 became the most powerful institution in Egypt. Besides its role in producing military hardware, industries owned by the military produces domestic hardware and own companies that compete for public projects such as construction, 100% self-sufficient in agricultural projects and own private gas stations as well. This makes it the most powerful institution, with its income all circulated within the institution, and is off-budget in addition to the budget being completely secretive. **Figure (3)** illustrates military personal, as the number of troops under the command of the national government, intended for use against foreign adversaries, and ready for combat as Jan 1, 2012. About 439.000 in Egyptian Army and 295.000 in Syrian Army, this number has influenced the situation in Egypt where the army was able to control the demonstrations and the borders from extremism flow to attack the important targets in the country.

Figure (4) Political Stability -No Violence

Source: World Bank Governance Indicators

Figure (4) shows that the Syrian regime replied to popular demands with a military strategy and was not prepared to pursue a more reform-oriented approach. Based on its previous strategy of preventing independent activity, has made the political organization of the citizen difficult and more authoritarian and less open to political reforms since the outbreak of the conflict.

The Syrian Army has fought against ISIS in several parts of the country and expelled it from the ancient city of Palmyra in March 2016. The location of Syria was an important trigger to be a fragile state. The ruling elites and their cronies allowed corruption to further widening inequality in Syria. The most significant when it comes to security and provision of daily service. But in Egypt, the situation is different even though the Egyptian Army supported the demonstrations from the first day and kept the sovereignty of the state from any external intervention.

Conclusion

All the factors leading to the outbreak of violent conflict from civil war and rebellion are in Syria. There is a high possibility that fighting in Syria, if left unrestricted, will extend to Jordan and Turkey, where the two countries are involved in providing foreign aid to the rebels, both of which serve as hosts of large numbers of refugees with ethnic ties to the people.

The fragility of neighbouring countries refugee, populations, and internal support were the most important factors mentioned in the literature; however, researchers also referred to additional variables as contributors to the conflict. The impact of violence has already spread to Lebanon because Hezbollah supported the Assad regime in Damascus and the exacerbation of the permanent and complex sectarian violence between Sunnis and Shiites in Iraq, where armed militants demand land in the West.

The strengthening of armed groups such as al-Qaeda and the Nusra Front in the border areas of eastern Syria and western Iraq does not augur well for the stability of Baghdad or the region, which is seen as an extended part of a cohesive dynamic as a full and predictable battle for Sunni-Shia survival - as well as an opportunity for either side to attack Israel, the narrow geography of the region, where everyone is close, makes it easy to spread the monuments.

THE FUTURE OF THE CONFLICT WILL TAKE FOUR CONSEQUENCES

A fragile peace: Central rule, low violence: After the overthrow of Assad in a palace coup, the former Assad regime confirmed the control of its militias and defeated the remnants of the fugitives. The Syrian parties, except the designated terrorist groups, return to the negotiating table and reach a peace agreement that includes a federal regime ruled by Syrian Government of National Unity GNU backed by a United Nations peace process. Due to some stability in this scenario, the reconstruction process is gaining more traction slowly, and overall, the situation in Syria is improving slightly.

Reconquista: After the breakdown of peace talks in Geneva and Astana, the fighting intensified and became more brutal than ever. After signs that moderate Sunni Arab opposition groups were using chemical weapons against civilians, the West withdrew its support. Assad's forces gain momentum and regain control of most of Syria. In areas controlled by the government, severe civil repression, terrorist attacks, and repeated bombings. Assad's regime is waging a tough war to restore the remaining rebel-held areas.

Warlords: fragmented Rule, severe violence: After the liberation of Raqqa, the break of the siege of Deir al-Zour, and the regional defeat of ISIS, international representatives. However, with the return of differences between the various Syrian parties. As the situation deteriorates, the government and opposition forces collapse and the country becomes a mix of feudalism. All domestic politics, there are regular violent clashes between warlords. International actors are reluctant to intervene in the conflict.

Frozen conflict: Fragmented rule and low-intensity violence: After extensive ethnic cleansing, international and regional actors pressed their proxies to accept a ceasefire. A peace deal on Syria's future seemed impossible. Violence in Syria is declining and conflict is virtually frozen. The country is divided into a

separate, stateless state, each supported by different regional and international players. In some areas, the economic situation and good governance are improving, while conflict continues in other regions.

5. *POLICY IMPLICATIONS*

- Start national reconciliation and dialogue among different political organizations under UN and Arab league mediation.
- The international community and Arab league should assist the central government and political interest groups to form an inclusive government, support in rehabilitation and reconstruction of Syria, assist refugees in neighbouring countries and provide support during repatriation, and provide development projects to the repatriated refugees.
- Regional peace conference should be organized to combat cross border security insurgency to bring peace and stability to Syria and the Middle East through consensus of all the neighbouring countries based on future common regional benefit rather than individual interest is imperative.

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All Praises and Thanks Go to My Mother the Secret of My Superiority and My Success.

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